

1 **The effect of induced queen replacement on *Nosema* spp. infection in honey bee (*Apis mellifera***
2 ***iberiensis*) colonies**

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24 **Running title: Queen replacement influences *Nosema* infection in honey bee colonies**

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27 **Summary**

28 Microsporidiosis of adult honeybees caused by *Nosema apis* and *Nosema ceranae* is a common worldwide
29 disease with negative impacts on colony strength and productivity. Few options are available to control the
30 disease at present. The role of the queen in bee population renewal and the replacement of bee losses due
31 to *Nosema* infection is vital to maintain colony homeostasis. Younger queens have a greater egg laying
32 potential and they produce a greater proportion of uninfected newly eclosed bees to compensate for adult
33 bee losses; hence, a field study was performed to determine the effect of induced queen replacement on
34 *Nosema* infection in honey bee colonies, focusing on colony strength and honey production. In addition, the
35 impact of long-term *Nosema* infection of a colony on the ovaries and ventriculus of the queen was
36 evaluated. Queen replacement resulted in a remarkable decrease in the rates of *Nosema* infection,
37 comparable with that induced by fumagillin treatment. However, detrimental effects on the overall colony
38 state were observed due to the combined effects of stressors such as the queenless condition, lack of brood
39 and high infection rates. The ovaries and ventriculi of queens in infected colonies revealed no signs of
40 *Nosema* infection and there were no lesions in ovarioles or epithelial ventricular cells.

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42 **Keywords-** *Nosema ceranae*, honey bee queen, *Nosema* control, beekeeping

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53 1. Introduction

54 Microsporidia comprise a large phylum of fungal-related pathogens that have been widely studied over the
55 last decade (Keeling and Fast, 2002; Texier et al. 2010). These pathogens are unicellular spore-forming
56 obligate intracellular parasites of all major animal lineages, including humans, insects and fish (Didier and
57 Bessinger, 1999; Kent and Speare, 2005; Williams, 2009; Valles et al., 2011). *N. ceranae* was recently
58 identified as a microsporidian parasite of *Apis mellifera* (Higes et al., 2006; Huang et al., 2007) and
59 microsporidiosis due to this pathogen now represents a major disease of honey bees in some climates
60 (Higes et al., 2008; Heintz et al., 2011). The incidence of this disease has increased dramatically in many
61 regions of the world (OIE, 2010), prompting a recent reconsideration of its sanitary status by the World
62 Organization for Animal Health (OIE, 2011). Nevertheless, differences in virulence at the individual bee level
63 have been described following experimental infection (Paxton et al., 2007; Higes et al., 2007; Chen et al.,
64 2009; Forsgren and Fries, 2010), which may reflect the use of different experimental approaches (Forsgren
65 and Fries, 2010). The severity of infection at the colony level can also vary considerably (Cox-Foster et al.,
66 2007; Higes et al., 2008; Fries, 2010; Bacandritsos et al., 2010; Bromenshenk et al., 2010; Gisder et al., 2010;
67 Williams et al., 2010). In field conditions, at the colony level, infection by *N. ceranae* and its ultimate impact
68 on colony health may be influenced by multiple factors. One of these factors may be related to the honey
69 bee colony homeostasis and the role of the queen in bee population renewal and the rate at which she can
70 replace forager bee losses due to *Nosema* infection (Moeller, 1978; Khoury et al., 2011).

71 Honey bee colonies are composed of related and closely interacting individuals that form a highly complex
72 society (Khoury et al., 2011). Colonies feature a haplodiploid sex determination system, whereby queen-
73 worker differentiation is nutritionally determined during the larval stage (Kamakura, 2011). Queens have
74 the longest lifespan, approximately 2 years, although lifespans of up to 8 years have been reported (revised
75 by Page and Peng, 2001). Queens become sexually mature 6 days after emergence and embark upon
76 orientation and mating flights (Remolina and Hughes, 2008). They mate with 10-12 drones (Tarpy and
77 Nielsen, 2002) and store enough sperm to fertilize eggs for their entire lifespan (Woyke, 1960). Sperm
78 remains fertile for several years in the spermatheca of the queen, although in older queens (over one year

79 old) spermatozoa move slowly and exhibit a lower metabolic profile (Al-Lawti et al., 2009). Vigorous queens
80 lay eggs abundantly (1,500-2,000 eggs per day) in periods when the pollen supply is high, and they maintain
81 this laying capacity for at least one year (Snodgrass, 1956; Winston, 1987; Richard et al., 2007; Remolina
82 and Hughes, 2008). Moreover, younger queens have a greater egg laying potential (Woyke, 1984; Prost
83 1989; Phillipe, 1990; Aykol et al., 2007, 2008) and thus, they tend to form larger colonies that produce more
84 honey than those headed by older queens (Woyke, 1984; Harris, 2010) and tend to be less severely affected
85 by certain honeybee diseases such as noseosis (Moeller, 1978; Pickard and El-Shemy, 1989).

86 As the queen is the only reproductive female in the colony, her loss means imminent colony death if a
87 replacement is not provided. The replacement of killed or damaged reproductive bees in monogynous
88 colonies is accomplished by the worker honeybees (Butler, 1957; Winston, 1979), who rear replacement
89 reproductive bees from existing immature stages within the first 48 hours after queen loss (Fell and Morse,
90 1984; Hatch et al., 1999).

91 In the present work we describe the effect of induced queen replacement on the development of *Nosema*
92 infection in honey bee colonies in field conditions and on colony strength and honey production. The
93 impact of long-term *Nosema* infection of the colony on the ovaries of the queen was also studied.

94

95 **RESULTS**

96 **First trial: The effect on the queen of colony infection by *Nosema* spp.**

97 ***Evolution of *Nosema* infection in experimental colonies.***

98 In September 2007, all 20 experimental colonies were infected by *N. ceranae*, 10 of which were co-infected
99 with *N. apis*.

100 One month after the first series of treatment (group A, 10 colonies) or vehicle (group B, 10 colonies)
101 applications (see fig. 1), *Nosema* spp. were no longer detected in 7 of the 10 fumagillin-treated colonies,
102 while the remaining 3 were still infected with *N. ceranae* alone. The mean percentage of forager bees in
103 group A colonies infected with *N. ceranae* averaged 26.6%. Within the same period, no changes were

104 observed in the infected status of any group B control colonies, which displayed a mean rate of infection of
105 62.5% (Table 1).

106 Analysis of the composite forager samples (n=20) in October 2008, after application of fumagillin or vehicle
107 the previous month, revealed that only one fumagillin-treated colony remained infected with *N. ceranae*.
108 By contrast, all group B colonies were still infected by *N. ceranae*, one of which was co-infected with *N. apis*
109 (Table 1).

110 When the individual forager and house bees were analyzed before intervention in April 2009 (Fig. 1), there
111 were more infected bees in the non-treated colonies (group B) than in treated ones (group A), with 74%
112 (Range = 55-95%) of the foragers and 48.5% (Range = 0-80%) of the house bees presenting *Nosema*
113 infection in the group B, whereas 42% (Range = 25-70%) of foragers and 4.5% (Range = 0-15%) of the house
114 bees were infected in group A (Table 1). At this time all the group A colonies were infected with *N. ceranae*,
115 two of which were co-infected with *N. apis*. In group B, all the colonies were infected by *N. ceranae*, one of
116 which was co-infected with *N. apis*.

117

118 ***Histopathological analysis of queens***

119 No lesions were observed in the ovarioles or epithelial ventricular cells (Fig. 2C') of queens removed from
120 colonies from groups A (Fig 2 A-D) or B (Fig. 2 A'-D'). In both groups, parallel ovarioles with a normal and
121 well differentiated germarium and vitellarium were observed, and normal differentiation of the ovarioles
122 was evident (Fig. 2 A, A'). In general, no cellular disorganization was observed in the follicles, as well as no
123 increase in intracellular spaces and no paracrystalline arrays in the peritoneal epithelium. Healthy follicle
124 cells clustered around the egg cells alternated with nurse cells in a normal pattern. Moreover, the follicle
125 size increased as development proceeded (Fig 2 A,D - A',D'), and as the eggs approached the oviducts,
126 nurse cells began to shrink and degenerate (Fig 2 B,B' - C,C'). *Nosema* spp. spores were not detected in the
127 ovaries or ventriculi of the queens from either group.

128 No cell death was evident in the anterior portion of each ovary when TUNEL assays were performed (Fig. 3
129 A, A'), whereas a normal increase in apoptotic cell death was observed in nurse cells (TUNEL positive) that

130 was correlated with the degree of egg maturation (Fig. 3 B,B'-C,C'). The number of dead cells did not
131 increase in any of the queen tissues analyzed that might be indicative of viral or *Nosema* infection.

132

133 **Second assay: Effect of queen replacement on the evolution of *Nosema* infection.**

134 As described in the experimental procedures, each group was further subdivided into two groups, A1, A2,
135 B1 and B2; the letter representing the original treatment group, while the number indicates the queen's
136 status (1 = original queen removed and replaced by newly born queen; 2 = original two year-old queen still
137 present). When bee samples collected in April 2009 were analyzed before the queen was manipulated (Fig.
138 1), significant differences were found between the infection rates in foragers from non-treated (groups B1
139 and B2) and previously treated (groups A1 and A2) colonies. Thus, percentage of infected foragers of groups
140 B1 ($73 \pm 15.2\%$, mean \pm s.d., range = 55-95%; $P < 0.003$) and B2 ($75 \pm 16.9\%$, range = 55-95%, $P < 0.05$) were
141 significantly greater than those of groups A1 ($46 \pm 15.6\%$, range = 30-50%) and A2 ($38 \pm 10.9\%$, range = 25-
142 55%; Fig. 4). The same situation was observed in the case of house bees collected in April 2009, where
143 average of bees infected was significantly higher in groups B1 ($42 \pm 24.1\%$, range = 20-70%; $P < 0.05$) and B2
144 ($63 \pm 18.9\%$, range = 0-80%; $P < 0.001$) when compared with those in groups A1 ($8 \pm 7.6\%$, range = 0-15%)
145 and A2 ($1 \pm 2.2\%$, range = 0-5%; Fig. 5).

146 Samples were collected from the different colonies in June 2009, after treatment (A2) and syrup (B2)
147 application and after allowing sufficient time for spontaneous requeening and the establishment of a
148 normal brood pattern in the A1 and B1 colonies. When these samples were analysed there were significant
149 differences between groups regarding infection rates of forager bees ($F = 17.2$, $P < 0.0001$). Forager bees
150 from group B2 (control colonies with original queen present) exhibited a significantly higher infection rate
151 ($72 \pm 12.5\%$, range 50-80%; $P < 0.0001$) than those from groups A1 ($28 \pm 2.7\%$, range 25-30%), A2 ($17 \pm$
152 12.5% , range 5-35%) and B1 ($29 \pm 6.5\%$, range 25-40%). By contrast, no differences in infection rates were
153 observed between groups A1, A2 and B1 (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$). Moreover, contrary to the other groups, the
154 rate of infection in the Group B2 did not significantly decrease in the pre/post-treatment interval (Fig. 4).

155 House bees exhibited significantly lower rates of infection than forager bees, both in April 2009 ($F = 12.9$, P
156 $= 0.001$) and June 2009 ($F = 14.2$, $P = 0.001$), although intra-group comparisons revealed similar findings to
157 those of forager bees. It appeared that treatment application (A2) syrup supply (B2) and induced queen
158 replacement (A1, B1) tended to reduce the infection rates in the hive, although this decrease in the
159 pre/post-treatment interval was statistically significant only in the case of group B1 ($P = 0.004$; Fig. 5).
160 The post-treatment infection rate in group B2 ($39 \pm 22.2\%$, range 20-70%) was significantly higher than that
161 of group A1 (0%; $P = 0.003$), A2 (0%; $P = 0.003$) and B1 ($4 \pm 5.5\%$, range 0-10%; $P = 0.01$), but it did not differ
162 significantly to that of the pre-treatment situation ($63 \pm 18.9\%$, range 40-80%; $P = 0.273$; Fig. 5). Symptoms
163 of chalkbrood disease were observed in two colonies of group B2, one of which collapsed in August 2009
164 and that left no remaining adults inside the hive. In April 2009, 95% of the forager bees from this colony
165 were infected by *Nosema* spp.

166

167 ***Adult bee population and brood production***

168 During the 6 months of the pre-trial period (October 2008 - April 2009) the size of the adult bee populations
169 between colonies did not differ significantly (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$; Fig. 6). Between the end of April 2009 and
170 July 2009, a period coinciding with maximum bee activity and honey production, the adult bee populations
171 from groups A1 and A2 were significantly higher than those of groups B1 and B2 (ANOVA, $P < 0.05$). By
172 contrast, no such differences were observed in September and October 2009, although colonies from
173 groups A1 and A2 still presented a trend for higher levels of adult bee population. On the whole there were
174 no significant differences in the brood production between groups (Fig. 7), regardless of the operation
175 applied to them (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$), except for May 2009 when queenless colonies (groups A1 and B1)
176 underwent a broodless period and presented a significantly lower brood production (ANOVA, $P < 0.0001$).
177 By spring of 2010, one year after treatment application and/or queen removal, two colonies had collapsed:
178 one each from groups B1 and B2. Two months before collapse in March 2010, the B1 colony contained only
179 drone brood (colony with laying workers or a drone-laying queen). When both the collapsed colonies were
180 excluded from the comparisons, groups A1 (9.4 ± 1.14 combs with adult bees; $U = 3$, $P = 0.047$), A2 ($9.6 \pm$

181 0.89 combs with adult bees; $U = 1$, $P = 0.018$) and B1 (9.3 ± 0.58 combs with adult bees; $U = 0$, $P = 0.029$)
182 were significantly more populated than the group B2 colonies (7.5 ± 0.58 combs with adult bees; Fig. 8) at
183 this time point. No significant differences in the number of brood cells were found between groups ($\chi^2 =$
184 1.79 , $P = 0.62$).

185

186 **Honey production**

187 There were significant differences in the mean honey production between groups in 2009 ($\chi^2 = 10.3$, $P =$
188 0.016 ; Fig. 9), with A2 colonies producing significantly more honey than those of groups B1 ($U = 1$, $P =$
189 0.016) and B2 ($U = 4$, $P = 0.046$). The highest level of honey was produced by colonies in groups A2 ($26.22 \pm$
190 7.47 kg/colony) and A1 (20.63 ± 2.79 kg/colony) when compared to that produced by those in groups B2
191 (18.64 ± 5.23 kg/colony) and B1 (12.10 ± 2.48 kg/colony). One of the colonies of group B1 failed to produce
192 any honey for unknown reasons, while one colony of group B2 produced no honey due to colony death
193 before harvesting. Both non-productive colonies were excluded from the analysis of honey production.

194 As in 2009, significant differences in honey production were recorded between the experimental groups in
195 2010 ($\chi^2 = 9.3$, $P = 0.026$; Fig. 10). Colonies of group B2 were significantly less productive than those of
196 group A1 ($U = 1$, $P = 0.027$) and A2 ($U = 0$, $P = 0.014$). As in 2009, the highest levels of honey production
197 were recorded in colonies of groups A2 (22.2 ± 5.71 kg/colony) and A1 (19.29 ± 4.9 kg/colony). However,
198 unlike the previous year the mean honey production of group B1 (17.98 ± 9.84 kg/colony) was higher than
199 that of group B2 (9.17 ± 5.89 kg/colony), although this difference failed to reach statistical significance
200 (Fig.10).

201

202 **DISCUSSION**

203 The present study demonstrates the central role of the queen in the evolution of *N. ceranae* infection of
204 honey bee colonies. Indeed, the removal of the queen and the subsequent replacement with a younger
205 queen decreased the proportion of *Nosema*-infected forager and house bees, which maintained the overall
206 infection at a level compatible with colony viability. This effect should be taken into account when studying

207 the evolution of *Nosema* disease in different geographical areas in which queen replacement (either
208 naturally or by the beekeeper) frequently occurs. The emergence of brood is the primary natural defence
209 against *Nosema*, allowing replacement of infected bees with healthy young bees, and thus, colonies with
210 vigorous young queens are less prone to suffer *Nosema* infection (Moeller, 1978). Our results are consistent
211 with these observations and the beneficial effects of *Nosema* control over the development of bee colonies
212 and the final production of honey are demonstrated in the present assay, since colonies in which nosemosis
213 was controlled were the most vigorous and productive.

214 The health and fitness of a honey bee colony depends greatly on the quality of the queen (*i.e.*, mating
215 ability, fecundity and offspring viability), as she is the only reproductive female in the colony and she is
216 therefore responsible for the constant renewal of the worker bee population (Gilley et al., 2003; Gauthier
217 et al., 2011). The age of a queen and the variation in her reproductive potential are important factors
218 influencing the honey bee life-cycle (Tarpy et al., 2000). Ageing has an impact on the reproductive status of
219 the queen, decreasing her egg-laying potential (Butler, 1957; Philippe, 1990; Akyol et al., 2007, 2008) and
220 the quantity and condition of stored sperm (Page and Peng, 2001; Al-Lawati et al., 2009). Moreover, honey
221 bee queens undergo physiological changes with age that may affect their pheromone output (Rhodes et al.,
222 2007), which in many cases reflects their reproductive status. These subtle differences can be detected by
223 worker honey bees, who are more responsive to queens with a higher reproductive potential, in turn
224 influencing various aspects of their behaviour and physiology (Kocher et al., 2009). Hence, to maintain
225 colony health and survival, and to increase strength and productivity, it is essential to ensure the presence
226 of young productive queens in colonies by regular replacement on an annual or biannual basis (Philippe,
227 1990; Invernizzi, 2006). This operation may be also beneficial to prevent health problems in the brood and,
228 as demonstrated here, to control infection by *Nosema* and its deleterious effects at the colony level.

229 *N. ceranae* is the aetiological agent of nosemosis type C, one of the most prevalent and economically
230 damaging honey bee diseases under certain conditions (Higes et al., 2008; Bacandritsos et al., 2010;
231 Bromenshenk et al., 2010; Higes et al., 2010; Heintz et al., 2011). Indeed, the negative effect of infection by
232 *Nosema* (primarily *N. ceranae* in this study) on both final honey production and the bee population are

233 demonstrated in the present assay. At the colony level, parasitization can affect essential colony tasks such
234 as brood care, thermoregulation, defence or foraging (Gauthier et al., 2011). In addition, the energetic
235 stress placed upon the host as result of an infection can compromise the immune response itself, allowing
236 other pathogens to invade the host and triggering a cascading effect (Mayack and Naug, 2009). Infection of
237 individual bees by *N. ceranae* has a clear effect at the colony level due to both behavioural changes induced
238 by infection and the continuous death of strongly infected bees (revised by Higes et al., 2010). Furthermore,
239 chronically high death rates of forager bees can result in rapid population decline (Khoury et al. 2011) and
240 in addition, the plasticity of the age polyethism in colonies means that sustained forager losses results in
241 hive bees joining the foraging population at much younger ages than normal (Huang and Robinson, 1996;
242 Amdam and Omholt, 2003; Woyciechowski and Morón, 2009). However, these precocious foragers are less
243 effective and resilient than normal foragers (Oskay, 2007). These negative effects of *Nosema* infection can
244 be controlled by the application of a *Nosema* treatment or by induced queen replacement, as described in
245 the present study.

246 In our experimental conditions, the percentage of forager and house worker bees infected by *Nosema* spp.
247 in spring was lower in colonies subjected to induced queen replacement. This effect was similar to that
248 observed following treatment of experimental colonies with fumagillin. Indeed, the high egg-laying
249 potential of younger queens (Moeller, 1978) has previously been shown to successfully control other brood
250 and adult bee diseases (Rahman, 1992; Aykol et al., 2007).

251 The marked effect of queen replacement on the percentage of *Nosema*-infected bees suggests that newly
252 eclosed queens were more efficient in renewing bee populations than older queens, resulting in
253 populations with higher proportions of young bees (Harris, 2008). Moreover, the hiatus in brood production
254 observed in these colonies may have altered the social structure of the colony. This in turn may influence
255 the transmission dynamics of the disease (Naug, 2008), hygienic behaviour (Evans and Spivak, 2010) and/or
256 the vitality and longevity of the bees, with positive effects on colony health. Further studies are required to
257 fully elucidate these potential effects.

258 In the colonies treated with vehicle solution alone (syrup, group B2), there were no significant changes in
259 either the percentage of infected foragers or house bees. These findings may indicate that supplementary
260 feeding with syrup does not decrease significantly the number of *Nosema*-infected bees, in agreement with
261 earlier reports (Avilez and Araneda, 2007; Hornitzky, 2008).

262 Interestingly, when composite samples of 30 bees were analyzed after the different manipulations in spring
263 2009, all 20 experimental colonies were infected to some degree, which may have indicated that
264 experimental interventions had no effect on overall colony infection. Nevertheless, significant differences
265 were observed in the percentage of infected bees between groups. Therefore, the analysis of the
266 percentage of infection in each colony rather than in a composite sample proves a more accurate marker of
267 the colonies health status, as reported previously (Doull, 1965; Pickard and El Shemy, 1989; Higes et al.,
268 2008; Meana et al., 2010).

269 There was a lower prevalence of *Nosema* infection in house bees than in foragers from the corresponding
270 colonies, in line with previous reports (L'Arrivee, 1963, Doull, 1965; Meana et al., 2010). Colonies treated
271 with fumagillin or in which the queen was replaced showed very low (group B1) or no signs of infection in
272 house bees (groups A1 and A2) after operations in spring 2009. This finding suggest that in these colonies
273 with lower *Nosema* infection rates the number of sick bees was inferior, and thus, the overall hive
274 performance and health status may present more optimal levels in comparison with colonies with higher
275 number of infected bees. Moreover, *Nosema* infection has been shown to affect the physiology and
276 behaviour of the infected honey bees, having an impact over their pheromones production (Dussaubat et
277 al., 2010), immune response (Antúnez et al., 2009), flight behaviour (Krajl and Fuchs, 2010), and inducing an
278 energetic stress (Mayack & Naug, 2009; Martín-Hernández et al., 2011a), behavioural fever (Campbell et al.
279 2010) and hunger-mediated conduct (Naug & Gibbs, 2009) at the individual level. Since variation in
280 individual honey bee behaviour and physiology relates to variation in colony state (Schmid-Hempel et al.,
281 1993, Khoury et al., 2011), all these factors affecting infected bees may cause damage at the social level and
282 have detrimental effects on colony homeostasis, and therefore, the less infected colonies may be less prone

283 to collapse (Higes et al., 2008) or to suffer other problems associated with more heavily infected colonies
284 (group B2).

285 In the present study, induced queen replacement involved the manual removal of the queen from the
286 colony, which was then naturally replaced but resulted in an interim broodless period of approximately 4
287 weeks. The alterations observed in the size of these colonies (mainly in group B1) were probably due to this
288 brood hiatus. Indeed, this effect was milder in colonies that had been treated the previous autumn with
289 fumagillin (group A1), which probably reflected the strength of the colony, as determined by the adult bee
290 population and *Nosema* infection level. These results suggest that stress, such as the absence of a queen, a
291 lack of brood and high infection rates, may combine to produce detrimental effects on general colony
292 conditions, such as those observed in colonies in group B1.

293 Colonies that received only syrup in both autumn and spring (group B2) remained highly infected
294 throughout the course of the experiment, and although these colonies were smaller, they produced similar
295 levels of brood to less-parasitized fumagillin-treated colonies (groups A1 and A2). *N. ceranae* infection has
296 been previously reported to reduce population size without affecting the brood area (Soroker et al., 2011),
297 which may reflect a higher rate of adult bee mortality in strongly-infected colonies. A short-term analysis
298 under laboratory conditions reported no differences in survival rates of uninfected versus *N. ceranae*-
299 infected foragers fed *ad libitum* (Mayack and Naug, 2009), and food availability was also suggested to mask
300 the mortality due to the energetic stress imposed by the pathogen (Naug and Gibbs, 2009). These studies
301 may not be comparable to the long-term assays in experimental field conditions described here, since we
302 did find that colonies with higher infection levels that received supplementary sugar syrup had a smaller
303 population and, probably, higher rates of adult bee mortality than colonies with lower infection levels.

304 As brood production did not significantly differ between the groups, the variations in colony population
305 size, mainly in untreated colonies (groups B1 and B2), are not likely to be due to differences in queen
306 fecundity. Furthermore, histopathological analysis of the queens removed did not reveal any indication of
307 degeneration in the ovaries due to viral infection (Gauthier et al., 2011), or signs of *Nosema* infection in the
308 ventriculi and ovaries (Liu, 1992). The decrease in the adult bee population size may be related to the

309 broodless period observed in colonies that lost their queen (group B1) or to the constant loss of infected
310 adult bees due to the pathogenic effects of *Nosema* in the case of the highly infected colonies (group B2;
311 Higes et al., 2008, 2009a, 2010; Mayack and Naug, 2010; Krajl and Fuchs, 2010; Suwanapong et al., 2010;
312 Dussaubat et al., 2010).

313 Honey production was affected by the sudden pause in brood rearing that followed queen removal and
314 thus, treated colonies of group A2 produced significantly more honey than colonies of group B1 in which
315 the queen was replaced. However, despite queen removal in spring 2009, group A1 colonies produced
316 similar levels of honey to those of A2 in which the queens were untouched.

317 The negative effects of brood hiatus on the bee population, and on brood and honey production, were no
318 longer evident one year after queen removal. Thus, in spring 2010 the colonies that had suffered queen
319 replacement in spring 2009 had adult bee populations and brood and honey production similar to those
320 treated with fumagillin one year before. Nevertheless, in the spring 2010, untreated colonies not subjected
321 to queen replacement in 2009 (group B2) exhibited a significantly smaller adult bee population, fewer
322 sealed brood cells and the lowest levels of honey production of all groups. These findings may suggest that
323 colony populations declined when workers died faster than they were replaced (Harris, 2010; revised by
324 Higes et al., 2010), in turn affecting honey production. Moreover, greater vitality and honey production was
325 seen in 2010 in the untreated colonies subjected to queen replacement in 2009 (B1) than those in which
326 the queen was untouched (B2), suggesting that colonies headed by younger queens developed faster and
327 attained higher adult bee populations, as previously reported (Harris, 2010).

328 As nectar and pollen collection depend on the state of the colony, larger colonies can store significantly
329 higher amounts each (Eckert et al., 1994). Indeed, we found that control of *Nosema* infection by fumagillin
330 application in autumn and spring (group A2) resulted in larger and more productive colonies. Similar results
331 were obtained when using a combination of fumagillin in autumn and induced queen replacement in spring
332 (group A1).

333 The absence of an adequate adult bee population could be associated with some degree of neglect in
334 essential colony tasks such as brood care, thermoregulation, social organization, social “immunity” and

335 survival (Evans and Spivak, 2010; Gauthier et al., 2011). These weaknesses in underpopulated colonies may
336 also alter CO₂ levels (Seeley, 1974) and reduce the average temperature of the brood chamber, in turn
337 promoting physiological and behavioral changes in adult bees (Tautz et al., 2003; Groh et al., 2004; Jones et
338 al., 2005) and infection by other opportunistic pathogens (Vojvodic et al., 2011). Indeed, such a scenario
339 may explain the chalkbrood infections detected in colonies in which *Nosema* infection was uncontrolled
340 (B2), as reported elsewhere (Hedtke et al., 2011). One of these colonies collapsed in August 2009 and was
341 found to contain a high proportion of *N. ceranae*-infected bees and a high proportion of brood affected by
342 chalkbrood disease. It is probable that colony viability was only sustained while the queen could replace the
343 infected adult bees that were dying due to *N. ceranae* infection.

344 In regions with a rich amount of meliferous flora, such as the Mediterranean area, there is a directly
345 proportional relationship between brood area at the end of winter and honey production some weeks after
346 (Prost, 1989; Fries, 1988). Periodic queen replacement with a young prolific queen helps hives remain
347 strong, healthy and productive, and it is a fundamental element of professional apiculture (Phillipe, 1990;
348 Invernizzi, 2006; Gauthier, 2011). In our experimental conditions, induced queen replacement in spring
349 significantly decreased the *Nosema* parasitic load on honey bee colonies. While some negative effects of
350 this management practice were observed on bee population and honey production, these had disappeared
351 within one year after queen replacement. Queen replacement with a mated queen may have prevented the
352 brood hiatus observed in orphaned colonies, as well as its consequences on the bee population, and on
353 brood and honey production. Further research is required to optimize queen replacement strategies and to
354 build upon the beneficial effects observed in *Nosema*-infected colonies.

355 In Spain, queen replacement is not a habitual management practice, although in many other countries this
356 is routinely performed every one or two years. Variations in the severity of *N. ceranae* infection in different
357 countries (Higes et al., 2008; Bacandritsos et al., 2010; Borneck et al., 2010; Bromenshenk et al., 2010;
358 Gisder et al., 2010) have in general been attributed to differences in the pathogenicity of the
359 microsporidian strains (Williams et al., 2010) or to other epidemiological factors (revised by Fries, 2010).

360 We propose that the existing differences in honey bee hive management practices, such as regular queen
361 replacement, may also contribute to this variation in nosemosis type C severity.

362

363 **EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES**

364 **Honeybee colonies**

365 Twenty *Apis mellifera iberiensis* colonies located in the experimental apiaries at the “Centro Apícola de
366 Marchamalo” (CAR) were monitored. All colonies were acquired as nuclei (5 combs with a newly eclosed
367 queen, brood, worker bees and food stores) by the same professional beekeeper in the spring of 2007. At
368 the start of the experiment, evaluation of brood diseases (American Foolbrood, European Foolbrood and
369 Chalkbrood disease) was performed by confirming the absence of clinical symptoms, and the absence of *V.*
370 *destructor* and *Nosema* spp. in the colonies was confirmed after analysis according to OIE methods (2004)
371 and Martín-Hernández et al. (2007) respectively.

372 The colonies were placed close to another apiary containing colonies naturally parasitized by *N. ceranae*
373 and/or *N. apis*, which acted as a natural source of infection for the new colonies. In September 2007, all the
374 colonies were evaluated for *Nosema* infection, collecting one sample of forager bees ($n \geq 30$) from the
375 entrance of each colony at noon (Meana et al., 2010). These 20 composite samples were processed, DNA
376 was extracted and analysed by PCR as described previously (Martín-Hernández et al., 2011b). Throughout
377 the study, *V. destructor* was controlled twice annually by treatment with amitraz (Apivar®) or flumethrine
378 (Bayvarol®) to prevent the negative effects of this parasite on colony health.

379

380 **First assay: The effect on the queen of colony infection by *Nosema* spp.**

381 ***Evolution of *Nosema* infection in experimental colonies.***

382 Upon detection of *Nosema* spp. infection in the 20 colonies (September 2007), each was randomly assigned
383 to 2 experimental groups of 10 colonies each. The interventions performed in each experimental group are
384 shown in Figure 1. Briefly, *Nosema* infection was controlled in group A colonies as described previously
385 (Higes et al., 2011): 4 applications of 30 mg fumagillin (Fumidil-B®) dissolved in syrup (1:1 sugar/water) per

386 hive in October 2007 and April and September 2008. Group B colonies were administered the vehicle alone
387 (syrup, 1:1 sugar/water) in parallel with group A, and thus served as controls. Each group was located in
388 separate apiaries one kilometre apart.

389 The applications were supplied in plastic bags placed over the brood chamber and individual colony
390 consumption was assessed weekly. Any unconsumed syrup was removed prior to administration of the
391 subsequent dose.

392 To determine the level of *Nosema* infection after administration of treatment or vehicle, the percentage of
393 infected bees present in every colony was evaluated in November 2007. To that end, a sample of foragers
394 ($n \geq 20$) was collected at the entrance of each of the 20 colonies and the abdomens of the bees were
395 analyzed individually ($n = 20$ bees per colony) by putting every single abdomen ($n = 400$) in a well of a 96-well
396 plate (Qiagen) with glass beads (2mm of diameter, Sigma) and 300 μ l of water (PCRq) and subsequently
397 shaking the 96-well plates for 6 minutes at 30Hz in a TissueLyser[®] (Qiagen). DNA was extracted and PCR
398 was performed as described previously (Martín-Hernández et al., 2011b).

399 Forager bees were again collected ($n \geq 30$) in the colonies in October 2008 and the 20 composite samples
400 were analyzed by PCR as described above.

401

402 ***Histopathological analysis of queens***

403 A histopathological study was performed to evaluate *Nosema* infection of the queens and to study the long-
404 term effects of infection in the colony on the queen's ovaries. The queens from five colonies selected at
405 random from each group (Fig. 1) were removed in spring 2009 to allow the colonies to rear an emergency
406 queen from the worker brood present in the combs.

407 Abdomens of the captured queens were dissected, the ovaries and ventriculi were removed and prefixed
408 for one hour in a solution containing 2% glutaraldehyde and 2.5% paraformaldehyde, and subsequently
409 they were then washed three times in phosphate buffer (PBS, pH 7.4) and stored at 4°C.

410 The tissues of interest were embedded in paraffin following standard protocols, and 4 μ m sections were
411 stained with haematoxylin-eosin for complete histopathological analysis (as described in Higes et al., 2007,

412 2009b). Apoptosis in the ovaries was determined with the TUNEL assay (Terminal deoxynucleotide
413 transferase mediated X-dUTP nick end labelling). Briefly, tissue sections (6 μm) which contained all the
414 stages of development of ovarioles were placed on silanized slides, deparaffinized and rehydrated through
415 an ethanol series before rinsing in phosphate buffered saline (PBS). The tissues were treated with
416 Proteinase K (20 mg/ml) for 15 min at room temperature and then with 0.1% (w:v) Triton X-100 in PBS for
417 10 min. The sections were then incubated in a humidified chamber for 1 h at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in darkness using the In
418 situ Cell Death Detection Kit (Roche), according to the manufacturer's instructions. Subsequently, the
419 sections were washed with PBS and mounted in Vectashield (Vector Labs) containing DAPI (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, Sigma)
420 and analyzed using an Olympus BX61 epifluorescence microscope equipped with filter sets for fluorescence
421 microscopy (Ultraviolet, UV; 365 nm, exciting filter UG-1). Photographs were obtained with an Olympus
422 DP50 digital camera and processed using Adobe Photoshop 7.0 software (Adobe Systems). Scanning
423 electron microscopy was performed using a Hitachi S-3000N with an energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyzer
424 attached (INCAx-sight, Oxford Instruments).

425

426 **Second assay: Effect of queen replacement on the evolution of *Nosema* infection.**

427 This assay began in April 2009, using the same colonies used in the previous trial (see section 2.2) as
428 summarized in Figure 1.

429 In spring 2009, the percentage of *Nosema* infected bees was assessed in samples of both forager ($n \geq 20$) and
430 house ($n \geq 20$) bees from each of the 20 colonies (Higes et al., 2008), analyzing the bees individually as
431 described previously (Martín-Hernández et al. 2011b). Each group was further subdivided into two groups,
432 A1, A2, B1 and B2; the letter representing the original treatment group, while the number indicates the
433 queen's status (1 = original queen removed and replaced by newly born queen; 2 = original two year-old
434 queen still present).

435 The colonies in groups A1 and B1 successfully reared new queens. The colonies of group A2 received 4
436 weekly doses per colony of 30 mg fumagillin (Fumidil-B[®]) dissolved in syrup, and B2 colonies received the
437 vehicle alone (syrup) in parallel with colonies of group A2. The first doses of treatment or syrup were

438 administered on the same day as the queen was removed from groups A1 and B1. Syrup consumption was
439 recorded weekly in groups A2 and B2.

440 To evaluate the effectiveness against *Nosema* of the different treatments and queen replacement, *Nosema*
441 infection of forager and house bees was re-assessed after a period deemed sufficient for the newly eclosed
442 queens to restore a normal brood area in groups A1 and B1. Colony strength was estimated on the basis of
443 the number of combs containing adult bees and the number of brood cells (Higes et al., 1999). Monthly
444 assessments were carried out from October 2008 to October 2009 (except in August 2009), and a final post-
445 trial assessment was made in April 2010.

446 Honey production was evaluated in each colony at the end of the harvest season, in September 2009 and
447 September 2010. The frames containing honey from each colony were weighed separately and the total
448 amount of stored honey calculated as the difference in comb weight before and after extraction.

449 During each colony check, the queen's status and any clinical indications of infections other than *Nosema*
450 were noted.

451

452 ***Statistical analysis***

453 The percentage of parasitized bees, the size of the adult honey bee population, the number of brood cells
454 and the amount of honey produced by each experimental group were compared by one-way analysis of
455 variance (ANOVA) or the Kruskal-Wallis test (K-W), depending on the number of observations and the
456 distribution of the data. Where necessary, ANOVA was followed by Bonferroni or Tamhane posthoc tests,
457 depending on the homogeneity of variance in each case (Levene's test). The Mann-Whitney U-test was used
458 for two-sample comparison in cases where K-W non-parametric tests were used. Differences were
459 considered statistically significant when $\alpha = 0.05$.

460 Colony strength was reassessed in April 2010, one year after treatment of *Nosema* infection and/or queen
461 removal in spring of 2009. The adult bee population and brood area data recorded in spring 2010 were
462 analyzed using a K-W non-parametric test ($\alpha = 0.05$) and the Mann-Whitney U-test for two-sample
463 comparison. Differences in honey production in each group were determined by the same approach.

464 All analyses were carried out using SPSS software version 18.0.

465

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775 **TABLES AND FIGURES**

776 Table 1. *Nosema* infection during the first trial (queen study) before queen removal in April 2009 (n =
 777 number of colonies; * after application of fumagillin (group A) or syrup (group B); ** before intervention in
 778 the colonies in the spring of 2009).

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GROUPS	COLONIES	n	NOVEMBER 2007*		OCTOBER 2008*	APRIL 2009**		
			No. Colonies infected	% Forager bees infected	No. Colonies infected	No. Colonies infected	% Forager bees infected	% House bees infected
Group A	10		3	26,6	1	10	42	4,5
Group B	10		10	62,5	10	10	74	48,5

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782 Figure 1. Chronology of the experimental procedures followed in the study.

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N	Number of colonies	●	Data collection of adult bee population and brood production
★	Bee samples collection and PCR analysis of bee composite samples	♀	Induced queen replacement/Histopathological analysis queen ovaries
☆	Bee samples collection and PCR analysis of individual bees	■	Treatment against <i>Varroa destructor</i>
▲	Treatment against <i>Nosema</i> spp. (Fumidil-B [®])	◆	Data collection of honey production
△	Syrup supply (water-sugar 1:1)	N.D.	No data / No data recorded this month

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797 Figure 2. General histology of the ovarioles from group A and B queens showing the germarium (a), the
 798 beginning of the vitellarium (b) and a well-differentiated vitellarium (c). Note the disposition of the oocyte
 799 (oo) with the follicle (fc) and nurse cells (nc) in the ovariole. Nurse cell death (arrows) is observed as the
 800 eggs approach the oviducts. D, D', Details of the ovarioles showing the oocyte with the follicle and the
 801 nurse cells. No *Nosema* spp. spores were detected in ovarioles and ventriculi (asterisk). Scale bars of A,A'-
 802 C,C' = 300 μ m, D,D' = 50 μ m.

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823 Figure 3. Hoechst staining (H-33258) and apoptotic cells labelled by TUNEL reaction in ovaries from queens
824 from groups A (A,A') and B (B',B'-C,C'). The amount of clustered TUNEL labelled nurse cells increased with
825 egg maturation (A,A'-B,B') and many dead cells were detected close to the oviducts. The morphology of the
826 apoptotic cells was more evident at higher magnification in C,C'(inserts). Scale bars = 300 μ m.
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832 Figure 4. Mean percentage of parasitized forager bees in each group in spring 2009. A1 = queen
 833 replacement; A2 = fumagillin application; B1 = queen replacement; B2 = syrup supply; PRE = before
 834 fumagillin or syrup application or queen replacement; POST= after fumagillin or syrup application or queen
 835 replacement; * indicates statistically significant differences in the pre-post treatment interval.

845 Figure 5. Mean values of the percentage of parasitized house bees in each group in spring of 2009. A1 =
 846 queen replacement; A2 = fumagillin supply; B1 = queen replacement; B2 = syrup supply PRE = before
 847 fumagillin or syrup application or queen replacement; POST = after fumagillin or syrup application or queen
 848 replacement.

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858 Figure 6. Evolution of adult bee populations in each experimental group of colonies.

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861 Figure 7. Evolution of brood production in each experimental group of colonies.

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867 Figure 8. Number of combs covered by adult bees and number of brood cells in each group of colonies in
868 April 2010.

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877 Figure 9. Bloxpot of the amount of honey produced per colony in each experimental group in 2009.

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894 Figure 10. Bloxpot of the amount of honey produced per colony in each experimental group in 2010.

